

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

Evaluation of new rices for kharif planting

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In low-lying, waterlogged aman areas, most farmers grow long-duration, tall, traditional rices during kharif. Seed is broadcast onto dry land that floods as the monsoon intensifies. Sometimes fields are flooded immediately after sowing or at early crop growth. Lack of suitable high-yielding varieties for these lands is a major constraint to increased production.

We evaluated 18 promising high yielding rices (16 semidwarf and 2 tall)

developed at CRRRI for their suitability for direct seeding in waterlogged areas and where there is early flooding. The rices had yielded well in transplanted conditions.

Dry seed was line sown at 60 kg/ha with 20 cm between lines and 30-50-50 kg NPK; ha was applied basally. Two days after sowing, the field was submerged by heavy rains. Of the 18 varieties, 14 grew and yielded well (see table).

CR1017 yielded highest with 3.6 t/ha, followed by CR1010 and CR1018. CR1017 had maximum panicle-bearing tillers/m² and less sterility than other varieties. Lodging caused low yields of Safri-17/IR20-1, T412/IR20, and Waikoku/IR1014-211. *✍*

Yield and important ancillary characters of 14 rice cultivars, Orissa, India.

Culture	Plant ht (cm)	Grains (no. / panicle)	Sterility (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Av panicle-bearing tillers/m ²	Grain yield (t/ha)
CR1009 (Pankaj/Jaganath)	98	179	19	20	183	3.0
CR1010 (Pankaj /Japanath)	112	217	22	23	173	3.3
CR1011 (Pankaj /Jayanath)	101	122	11	22	159	2.2
CR1017 (Pankaj /Jaganath)	116	167	11	23	186	3.6
CR1018 (Pankaj /Japanath)	115	203	9	24	169	3.3
CR1013 (Jaganath natural cross)	113	137	14	20	169	2.8
CR1020 (CR70 /Pankaj)	112	152	23	28	137	2.4
T412 /IR20-3	119	123	12	11	144	1.5
T412 /IR20-8-2	116	124	17	11	122	1.5
T412 /IR20-18-2	114	151	9	15	142	2.1
T412 /IR20-194	115	154	13	11	147	1.7
T412 /IR2041-3	122	182	20	14	137	1.8
Safri-17/IR20-1	137	145	25	19	167	1.2
Waikoku / IR1014-211	129	149	9	20	132	2.1

CD (5%) for comparison of yield = 0.267

Hang Feng, a new, short-statured keng rice grown near Shanghai

Cui Sho-Bai, Institute of Crop Breeding and Cultivation, Shanghai Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Shanghai, China

In Feb 1983, the Shanghai Municipal Crop Variety Examining and Approving

Commission released Hang Feng. The variety is now grown on more than 20,000 ha around Shanghai. It was developed at the Institute of Crop Breeding and Cultivation of SAAS.

Hang Feng is short-statured with firm culms; strong, erect leaves and tight leaf sheaths; and good tillering and heading ability. It responds well to high N

application and resists lodging. It is relatively tolerant of low temperature at meiosis and flowering. Leaves are light green and become yellowish-green during ripening. It has had few disease and insect problems. Yield is comparatively stable.

Hang Feng has superior grain quality and high milling percentage. Milled rice is broad, uniform, and white, with good flavor, suitable stickiness, good scent, and glossy appearance.

The variety is most commonly planted as a second crop (plant height 70-75 cm),

although it also is single-cropped (plant height 85-90 cm). Second crop growth duration is 140 d. A single crop takes about 160 d. Hang Feng yields about 5 t/ha as a second crop and may yield 30% more in a single-cropping system. *ℳ*

Performance of BW rices in the midcountry wet zone of Sri Lanka

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We evaluated 5 short-duration (90-100 d) BW rices for performance in the Sri Lanka midcountry wet zone (MZ) at Peradeniya in Jul-Oct 1982. BW272-6B, BW288-2, BW293-2, BW267-3, and BW267-7 were developed by the Bombuwela Regional Agricultural Research Station (BRARS) for the low country wet zone, mainly the Kalutara Galle and Matara districts.

Plant height, 1,000-grain weight, yield, number of productive tillers, and panicle length in the MZ were compared with similar data from BRARS, where the varieties were grown in Apr-Jun 1982 (see table). Fertilizer doses were the same at both sites.

Peradeniya is 490 m above sea level and Bombuwela is 3 m above sea level. Average monthly temperature and rainfall at the sites are in the figure. The

Performance of BW rices at Peradeniya and BRARS.^a

Variety	Plant ht (cm)		Productive tillers (no.)		Panicle length (cm)		1000-grain wt (g)		Grain wt per plant	
	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B
BW 272-6B	102.8	100.5	2.4	5.0	25.6	26.36	16.1	16.7	4.02	5.75
BW 288-2	52.3	66.51	3.3	4.0	16.1	20.4	27.7	29.8	4.78	8.60
BW 293-2	59.0	66.01	1.9	3.0	9.5	22.8	27.2	30.0	3.21	7.80
BW 267-3	75.8	77.09	2.1	5.0	22.1	20.08	30.1	30.6	4.49	9.20
BW 266-7	94.0	81.56	2.2	4.0	21.8	21.71	25.4	25.8	2.03	5.68

^a P = av of 60 plants (20/replication) were analyzed at Peradeniya. B = data obtained from BRARS.

Monthly precipitation and temperature in Bombuwela and Peradeniya, Sri Lanka. 1982.

soil at Peradeniya is an alluvial gley.

The varieties performed poorly in the MZ, and took longer to mature than at BRARS. BW272-6B, normally a 90-d variety, matured in 122 d. All the varieties retained their insect and diseases resistance. BW267-3 yielded highest at both sites.

The differences in yield and maturity may have been caused by differences in location, that could have attributed to differences in humidity, sunshine hours, rainfall, day-night temperature, and irrigation water quality. *ℳ*

Manhar, high yielding, early maturing rice for the irrigated plains of Uttar Pradesh

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Manhar (UPR103-44-2) was developed using the pedigree method after hybridization of IR24 and Cauvery. It is a semidwarf that matures in 123 d, and is suitable for the irrigated plains of Uttar Pradesh.

Table 1. Mean performance of Manhar in trials in Uttar Pradesh, India.

Trial ^a	Year	Mean yield (t/ha)			
		Manhar	Saket 4 (check)	Prasad (check)	Increase ^b (%) over check
VT-Early	1980	5.1	4.3	4.2	18
VT-Early	1981	4.5	—	4.3	3
VT-Early	1982	4.9	—	4.1	20
VT-Early	1983	4.6	—	4.3	5
VT-Early	1984	4.8	—	4.4	10
SVT-Early	1982	4.8	3.9	—	22
SVT-Early	1983	4.3	3.7	—	15
SVT-Early	1984	3.7	3.2	—	18
PVT-2 (AICRIP)	1982	4.9	3.3	Ratna	49
PTV-2 (AICRIP)	1983	3.1	2.3	Rasi	34
Mean Sites (no.)		4.6	3.9	4.2	
		61	29	33	

^a VT = Varietal Trials, SVT = Standard Varietal Trials, PVT = All India Coordinated Trials. ^b Mean of 17% over Saket 4, 8% over Prasad.